

PROBLEMS IN ENGINEERING COLLEGES – AN OVERVIEW

A Paper Presented By

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ABSTRACT

India has been the heart of learning in the world since ages. It has everything that is needed to make it the number one country in the field of education i.e. brains, manpower, infrastructure and vision.

Then what is it that inspite of having everything that is needed in our country itself, every year hordes of students are leaving our country for education in other countries?

There are several problems, which make a difference in the way our engineering institutes are functioning as compared to world's leading educational institutes.

An overview of several such problems and a possible solution is highly necessary. An attempt is made to discuss some of these problems in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

India has been the heart of learning in the world since ages. It has everything that is needed to make it the number one country in the field of education Then what is it that inspite of having everything that is needed in our country itself, every year hordes of students are leaving our country for education in other countries?

Is it the lack of brain?

No. If there would have been lack of brain in our country, why would the other countries out source work worth crores of rupees to our country or why would Indians be recruited in Multinational Companies at key positions all over the world?

Is it the lack of Manpower?

With a rate of increase in population that is amongst the highest in the world, can our country be short of manpower? We have ample manpower which can be utilized effectively.

Is it lack of Infrastructure?

With crores of rupees being spent in the field of education, how can there be lack of infrastructure?

Then what is it that is lacking in our country in general and technical institutes in particular that is causing our students to spend the lifetime savings (in most of the cases) of their parents to learn something in other countries? Can we not offer it here itself?

There are several problems, which can make a major difference in the way our engineering institutes are functioning.

Some of the problems experienced by the Engineering Colleges of Gujarat State can be listed as follows.

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* ADMISSION PROCEDURE

The Problem

As we are all aware, the number of Engineering Colleges goes on increasing every year with a number of self-finance colleges opening at various places in the state.

The choice of considering engineering as a profession for the students has become much more easier as compared to the other professions. Students who are not able to score very nicely at the XII standard exams can also opt for engineering on payment seats of private colleges.

But this increase in opportunity for the students has posed several problems for the administrative as well as academic activities in various engineering institutes.

Every year the admission to the various engineering colleges in the state including the private i.e. self financed institutes is given through a Joint Admission Committee at Ahmedabad. These admissions are given as per the merit number obtained based on the marks scored in the board exams.

The process of admissions continues for several days as the students are called for admission based on various categories i.e. Central Board, State Board, Reserved Category (SC, ST, SEBC, PH, Army men and Open etc.)

After the initial round of admissions, a reshuffling process is done where in the interested students are called again for the admission of the vacant seats. This vacancy of seats occurs either due to increase in the number of seats in any branch of an existing institute or in granting permission for starting a new institute.

Through this process, a number of students who have already taken admission in one of the branch of an engineering college may be called and given admission in any other branch of engineering in either the same institute or any other institute. Thus, a student who may not be getting a branch of his choice or a place of his choice may get another chance. The process of reshuffling is also carried out for several days and there are possibilities that one student may be reshuffled more than one times in this process.

For example, a student who has initially received admission in Civil Engg. at Vasad may get admission in Civil Engg. in M.S.University in the first round of reshuffling and then get admission in Electrical Engg. in some other institute. Thus eventually he may have studied for 10 days in Civil at Vasad, 7 days in Civil at M.S. University and may then continue his education in Electrical Engg. in any either the same institute or any other institute.

But by the time the student gets admission in Electrical Engg. it may have been atleast 4 weeks since the beginning of the teaching activity in that institute so eventually he loses those 4 weeks of teaching.

At the same time, some other student may be given admission in his place in Civil Engg. at Vasad as well as in M.S.University. By the time these students get admission in his place, it may be a similar case that he/she has missed at least 4-5 weeks of teaching activity in his institute.

If we consider the same problem from the teaching point of view, a teacher who has taught a student for 4 weeks now gets another new student. Thus the teacher finds it difficult to keep continuity in teaching as sometimes more than 50 % students are reshuffled in case of the branches that are filled up last. At the same time, whatever was taught to the previous students has to be repeated for the new students (atleast for the term work and practical classes at mass level and theory at personal level).

The Suggested Solution

In an era where the universities in other countries are not only offering admissions through internet on a mouse click but are also giving details of the size of room, kind of furniture and facilities that shall be given in hostels, the layout of the institute, information of infrastructure facilities, etc, is it viable that we waste valuable time, manpower and money by taking months in the admission procedure of a single student?

To start with we can atleast do the following:

1. As far as possible, the academic activity should be started only after the admission procedure is completely over. But if the present time schedule is followed, it leaves very little time to finish the syllabus if the teaching is finished parallel to the other classes i.e B.E. – II, III & IV. It is therefore needed that the admission procedure should be started as early as possible. For this purpose, the results of the Board Exams should be declared much before than the time they are being declared at present.
2. The total number of seats for which admission is to be given should be finalized before the process of admission is started so that the entire need of reshuffling itself is eliminated. No sanction for increase in number of seats or permission to start new institutes should be given once the admission procedure has been started.
3. The process of collecting forms should be made online in order to save time and valuable manpower and money.
4. For most of the Engg. Colleges, the syllabus is common at the first year level, but this syllabus is not the same in all the engineering institutions. If a common syllabus is made for all the branches of engineering in all the institutions atleast for the first year level, a student who has been reshuffled can continue in the new institute without missing whatever is covered (as he has been already studying the same topics at the previous institute). At the most he/she may suffer 1-2 days of teaching which can be covered very easily. At the same time this facility can also be beneficial to the teachers as the new student has already studied the topics in the previous institute.

***INFRASTRUCTURE FACILITIES**

The Problem

The infrastructure facility in most of the engineering institutes is either insufficient or out of date and needs immediate attention.

Most of the established institutes, many of which are government aided are having infrastructure facilities that are too old, and either needs immediate repair or replacement. At some places, there may not be adequate facilities at all.

The government tries to solve these problems with the help of various schemes like Modrob, IX plan, X plan etc. But the amount is sanctioned in phases divided over a large time span. As a result by the time the last phase is completed, the equipments in the first phase may become obsolete (especially if one is setting up a computer lab) or there may be many other equipments that may need immediate attention. Sometimes, the established process of procuring the equipment is also cumbersome and consumes a lot of time and paper work.

In case of self financed institutes during the initial phase of establishment, the institute may be short of funds and as a result may compromise on several aspects.

As a result of this, the quality of teaching may suffer and eventually it may be the students who are at a loss.

The Suggested Solution

1. A review of the existing facilities should be conducted at frequent intervals to find the problem areas.
2. Priorities should be decided and funds should be chanelized to help the institutes which are lacking in infrastructure rather than making the rich institutes more richer and better.
3. The process of releasing funds should be changed so that all the equipments can be purchased at a time to increase the effective utilization of the equipments.
4. The process of procuring the equipments should be made simpler and less cumbersome so that it can be finished faster giving effective utilization of time and money.

*** INDUSTRY – INSTITUTE INTERACTION**

The Problem

In most of the engineering institutes, the pattern of existing syllabus or teaching technique is such that the students are given theoretical information rather than practical knowledge. The topics that are taught can rarely be applied directly to the field. This theoretical knowledge is necessary but at the same time some incorporation of practical problems faced by the industries and their possible solutions should also be included.

The Suggested Solution

1. Facility of Industry – Institute Collaboration should be given priority and should be encouraged such that industries come to the institutes with their problems and practical solutions should discussed / taught in the curriculum so that the students can apply it directly on the field.
2. Practical Training at various levels should be made compulsory for all branches of engineering for teachers as well as students. Students should be sent to various industries for training. At the same time, teachers should also be sent for practical training/ brain storming sessions at various industries so that collaboration can be obtained between academic as well as industrial institutions.

*** TEACHING STAFF**

The Problem

In most of the established / government aided engineering institutes, there is an acute shortage of properly qualified staff. Temporary / Adhoc / Part time staff is recruited in such institutes as the government either does not give permission to fill the posts or the process of recruiting permanent staff takes a long time. Due to this there is a constant reshuffling of staff members – it is very obvious that a person who is recruited as a Temporary / Adhoc / Part time staff is bound to search for better opportunity for personal stability and may leave the job within a short notice if he gets a better job.

According to the normal procedure, it may take several days before a new staff member is appointed in place of this staff member as the process again involves lot of paper work and time. Sometimes it may take months.

Under these circumstances, the teaching schedule which is going on normally may be affected as some other teacher may either be over-loaded for cope up for this shortage or a person who does not have the specialization may be asked to teach the topic. In both the cases, the final loss is borne by the students as ultimately it the quality of teaching that suffers.

In case of private / self financed institutions, there is a severe shortage of well qualified and experienced teachers during the initial years of establishment. It is obvious that the staff members from the existing established colleges may not be interested in leaving their jobs and joining such institutes. As a result, under qualified or inexperienced staff is recruited for the job. As the institute is a new one and is in an establishing stage, there are no previous experiences of past teachers which can be used by the new teachers / fresh inexperienced teachers, which again results in poor quality of teaching and loss to the students who have paid a very hefty amount of fees.

Also, in almost all the institutes, the student teacher ratio is not maintained due to several reasons. This also results in poor quality of education.

The Suggested Solution

1. The process of recruitment of teaching staff should be made faster and easier. Each faculty / institution should have the powers to recruit the teaching staff as soon as a post falls vacant so that the teaching schedule is not affected. As a result, the student teacher ratio can also be easily maintained.
2. The existing staff members should be motivated to attend more number of QIP programmes so that they can update their knowledge. The new / inexperienced staff members should be given training for the initial period. Incentives in the form of promotions can be given to increase the motivation of the existing staff members to upgrade their knowledge. There are several schemes like Carrier Advancement, 1:2:4 scheme etc. which are not implemented properly.
3. Evaluation of teaching techniques and syllabus should be done at frequent intervals to improve the quality of education.

CONCLUSION

As technocrats, we are the implementers of applied science. We must understand (take into consideration) the emerging needs of the society and apply our knowledge to cater to them. In a global village, with all multimedia facilities and advance technology and communication era, any TOM, DICK & HARRY can fetch a degree from anywhere in the world by sitting at his home. We need to do something that keeps us above these options in all situations by making slight changes in our existing functioning patterns.

Admission procedure should be made short and swift with no scope or need of reshuffling keeping in mind the previous experience of several years.

It is not that we cannot develop the infrastructure facilities to compete the international standards, we have the examples of IITs. Then why can't we give equal importance to all the educational institutes and cater to a mass rather than utilizing our skills and infrastructure to train just a few privileged students? There is a need to re-organize ourselves and pass on the

funds to the areas which are lacking the facilities rather than making the rich institutes more richer. At the same time instead of allowing mushrooming of new institutes, people should be encouraged to collaborate with the existing ones to improve their infrastructure.

There is no lack of exposure in technical fields in our country. But there is a severe lack of vision in our teaching staff. Regular interaction of the teaching staff with the industry should be made mandatory to enhance their teaching skills. This will help in developing a vision in the existing staff members. Industrial problems should be studied and incorporated in the curriculum to make the students aware of the problems as well as the solutions. This would not only give value to our education system but also increase job opportunities for our students.

Maintenance of student teacher ratio is the most essential aspect of quality education. This aspect can be taken care of by prompt recruitment of well-qualified and experienced staff.

If we are not equipped and competent to cater to the needs of tomorrow and are not fast enough to take our decisions, we shall soon be outdated. It is therefore high time for us to awaken and overcome such petty problems that are hampering our progress by behaving like anchors.

By doing this, we can not only ensure a better future for our institution, staff and students, but also for our country in the long run.